

AN INVESTIGATION INTO FATIGUE FAILURE AND SELF-LOOSENING OF BOLTED JOINTS SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE VIBRATION

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In bolted joints, it has been considered that fatigue failures occur after self-loosening occurs because in many cases the fatigue failures do occur after self-loosening has already occurred. However, self-loosening does not always occur before fatigue crack initiation. In this study focusing on the grip length which is the length between the first thread of bolt engaging with the internal thread and the bearing surface under the bolt head, we have investigated the thresholds of the grip length which determines the occurrence of self-loosening or fatigue failure. The investigations have been conducted using FE analyses based on transverse fatigue tests conducted in this study. Results show that the occurrence of self-loosening or fatigue failure is determined by the grip length. That is determined by whether the stress amplitude at the root of the first thread caused by the transverse vibration force applied to the bolted joint exceeds the fatigue strength of the bolt, or whether slippage occurs at the thread face and bearing surface of the bolt before the stress amplitude surpasses the fatigue strength.

Keywords: Bolted joint, Transverse fatigue, Self-loosening, Occurrence condition, Grip length

INTRODUCTION

Serious accidents due to fatigue failure and self-loosening of bolted joints have occurred in many fields (Nippon Hoso Kyokai [1] and Asahi Shinbun [2]). It is well-known that fatigue failure and self-loosening of bolted joints are important problems in machines, structures and other fields.. However, fatigue failure and self-loosening depend greatly on, not only, the material strength of the bolt material but also on the clamping force of the bolted joint. Since it is difficult to control the clamping force, it is not easy to consistently ensure the reliability of bolted joints.

The self-loosening of a bolted joint frequently occurs when the bolted joint is subjected to transverse vibration. Junker [3] first researched the self-loosening of bolted joints subjected to transverse vibration. Kasei *et al.* and Yamamoto *et al.* revealed experimentally that the bolt loosened with nut rotation when the thread surface and the bearing surface simultaneously slipped due to transverse vibration (Kasei and Sun [4], Yamamoto and Kasei [5] and Kasei *et al.* [6]). Izumi *et al.* simulated the bolted joint subjected to transverse vibration using 3 dimensional FE analysis and revealed the self-loosening mechanism (Izumi *et al.* [7] and Yokoyama *et al.* [8]). Jiang *et al.* [9] reported that the bolt elongated slightly due to strain ratcheting at the root of the first thread before

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the self-loosening occurred. From these results, we can deduce that the conditions for self-loosening are, simultaneously, slippage at the thread surface and at the bearing surface on a macroscopic level.

Incidentally, it is widely recognized that the fatigue failure of the bolted joint occurs because the clamping force decreases when self-loosening occurs. However, the question remains: *does self-loosening always occur before fatigue crack initiation?* To date, there have been few studies regarding the fatigue failure of bolted joints subjected to transverse vibration. Jiang *et al.* [10] indicated that the bolt broke when the bolt received comparative large transverse vibration in self-loosening tests. Conversely, Hashimura *et al.* [11] reported that self-loosening occurred after one percent of the fatigue life in a bolted joint subjected to transverse vibration. The results indicate that even if self-loosening occurred due to fatigue crack initiation, we might not have recognized that the self-loosening occurred before a fatigue crack initiated. Hashimura *et al.* [12, 13] also showed that the fatigue limit of a bolted joint under transverse vibration depends on the grip length, which is the length between the bolt bearing surface under the bolt head and the first thread that engages with the internal thread of the nut or fixture. Furthermore, Hashimura *et al.* [14] suggested that fatigue failure never occurs before self-loosening if the grip length is shorter than the nominal bolt diameter.

When we design bolted joints, if we know that fatigue failure or self-loosening is affected by grip length, we can prevent the occurrence of fatigue failure and self-loosening. In this study, we investigated the grip length thresholds in which self-loosening and fatigue failure occur by conducting FE analysis based on the transverse fatigue tests reported in our previous study [14].

FATIGUE TESTS OF A BOLTED JOINT SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE VIBRATION

Relationship between Apparent Fatigue Limit and Grip Length

First, we shall explain the effect of the grip length l_g of a bolted joint on the apparent fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$, which was investigated in our previous study [14]. Here, the apparent fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$ is the highest amplitude of transverse vibration for which the bolt does not break due to fatigue. Fig. 1 shows the schematic illustrations of the assembly of the bolted joints used in the experiments. The grip lengths of the bolted joints were $l_g=9$ mm, 12 mm, 17 mm and 22 mm. Each test bolt was a hexagon head bolt M10 with thread pitch 1.5 mm and fully threaded. The bolt property class was 8.8. The engaging thread length, l_e , with the internal thread part was $l_e=15$ mm. The test bolts were manufactured by cutting the bolts to $l=40$ mm in order to prepare the test bolts from the same batch. The bolt nominal lengths are expressed by the following equation.

$$l = l_g + 15 \quad (1)$$

For the bolted joint shown in Fig. 1, linear rollers were placed between the clamped parts in order to minimise friction losses, although actual bolted joints do not have linear rollers. Consequently, the bolts were directly loaded by the transverse force P_t through the bearing surface of the bolt. In the transverse fatigue tests, each test was conducted after the test bolt was tightened with an initial clamping force $F_i=15$ kN. In the experiments, the thread surface and bearing surface were lubricated with molybdenum disulfide grease. From the transverse fatigue tests, we were able to find the apparent transverse fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$.

Figure 2 shows the results of the transverse fatigue tests for the four types of bolted joint. In Fig. 2, the ordinate is the amplitude of transverse vibration force $\Delta P_t/2$ and the abscissa is the number of cycles to failure N_f . Symbol $\blacklozenge$ shows the result for $l_g=22$ mm, symbol $\blacktriangle$ shows the result for $l_g=17$ mm, symbol $\blacksquare$ shows the result for $l_g=12$ mm and symbol $\bullet$ shows the result for $l_g=9$ mm.

The white symbols show the results in which the bolts did not break without clamping force reduction. As shown in Fig. 2, the fatigue lives N_f increased when the amplitude of transverse vibration force $\Delta P_t/2$ decreased. In Fig.2 we call the highest amplitude of transverse vibration in

FIGURE 1 Bolted joints with different grip lengths used in the experiments.

FIGURE 2 Relationships between the amplitude of transverse vibration for the bolted joints with the different grip length and those fatigue lives

which the bolt does not break due to fatigue the apparent transverse fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$. It can be seen that the apparent transverse fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$ decreased with an increase in the grip length l_g . In the experiments, the main fatigue cracks in the broken bolts occurred at the root of the incomplete thread under the bolt head.

Figure 3 shows the apparent transverse fatigue limit $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$ for each grip length l_g . We can see in Fig. 3 that $(\Delta P_t/2)_w$ is linearly proportional to l_g .

FIGURE 3 Relationship between the apparent fatigue strength and the grip length

Analysis of Fatigue Failures

Figure 4 shows a schematic illustration of a deformed bolt due to the transverse force P_t . The bolt deforms in an S-shape if the bolt is loaded with a transverse force P_t . The bending moment diagram for this case can be drawn as in the right of Fig. 4, and the bending moment $M(x)$ is expressed by the following equation.

$$M(x) = (\Delta P_t/2) \cdot x - M_B \quad (2)$$

where M_B is the bending moment generated due to constraint by the engaging bolt threads and M_B is expressed as follows.

$$M_B = C \cdot (\Delta P_t/2) \cdot l_g \quad (3)$$

where C is a coefficient which is determined by the constraint in the engaging thread.

If the nominal length of the bolt is comparatively long and the bolt has a shank portion, the bolt breaks at the root of the first thread because the cross sectional area at the root of the first thread is smaller than that at the root of the incomplete thread. This is because the stress at the neck under the bolt head is lower than that at the root of the first thread although the bending moment at the neck under the bolt head is higher than that of the root of the first thread. But the bolts broke at the root of the incomplete thread under the bolt head in those cases because they were full thread bolts. In this case, it is not easy to derive the fatigue strength at the root of the incomplete thread because the shape

FIGURE 4 A deformed bolt model in a bolted joint subjected to transverse force

of the incomplete thread is complicated. Hence, in this study we assess whether the fatigue failure occurs or not using the nominal stress at the root of the first thread. This is because the relationship of the stress to the transverse force P_t is the same for each case if the coefficient C does not change greatly. Hence, let M_B be the bending moment at the root of the first thread, so the nominal stress σ_t at the root of the first thread is expressed by the following equation.

$$\sigma_t = \frac{M_B}{I_b} \cdot \frac{d_3}{2} = \frac{32M_B}{\pi \cdot d_3^3} \quad (4)$$

where I_b is a section moment of inertia at the root of the thread and d_3 is the diameter at the thread root.

In order to assess whether fatigue failure occurred or not, if σ_t expressed in Eq.(4) exceeds the fatigue strength σ_{fw} at the root of the first thread in the transverse direction, we can judge that the bolt failed by fatigue. We use the following equation proposed by Yoshimoto *et al.* [15] to derive the fatigue strength σ_{aw} in the axial direction of the steel bolt.

$$\sigma_{aw} = \frac{\sigma_{w0} \cdot (\sigma_T - \sigma_{0.2})}{K_f \cdot (\sigma_T - \sigma_{w0})} \quad (5)$$

where σ_{w0} is the fatigue strength of the bolt material, σ_T is the true ultimate strength of the bolt material, $\sigma_{0.2}$ is the proof strength of the bolt material and K_f is the fatigue notch factor at the root of the first thread for an M10 bolt.

For each parameter for an M10 bolt, the properties for class 8.8, shown in Table 1, are substituted into Eq.(5) and the axial fatigue strength can be obtained by

$$\sigma_{aw} = \frac{290 \times 10^6 \cdot (1370 \times 10^6 - 640 \times 10^6)}{3.56 \cdot (1370 \times 10^6 - 290 \times 10^6)} = 55.1 \text{ MPa} \quad (6)$$

The transverse fatigue strength σ_{fw} can be expressed by the following equation.

$$\sigma_{tw} = \frac{\sigma_{aw}}{K_L} = \frac{55.1}{0.923} = 59.7 \text{ MPa} \quad (7)$$

where K_L is a modification coefficient between axial fatigue strength and bending fatigue strength; we adopted $K_L=0.92$ (Socie [16]).

For the bolted joint subjected to transverse vibration, if the nominal stress σ_t due to transverse vibration force expressed by Eq.(4) exceeds the transverse fatigue strength, $\sigma_{tw}=59.7 \text{ MPa}$ expressed by Eq.(7), we can consider that the bolt broke. In this study, we derived the nominal stress σ_t at the root of the first thread by FE analysis of the bolted joint subjected to the transverse force P_t , and after that we have judged the fatigue failure by comparing the nominal stress σ_t for each transverse force P_t and σ_{tw} .

TABLE 1 Mechanical properties of test bolt (property class: 8.8)

Young's modulus E	Ultimate strength σ_u	Proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$	True ultimate strength of bolt material σ_T	Fatigue strength of bolt material σ_{w0}	Notch factor at the root of the first thread K_f
206 GPa	800 MPa	640 MPa	1370 MPa	290 MPa	3.56

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Elastic finite element analyses of the bolted joints subjected to a transverse force were conducted in order to reveal the threshold at which fatigue failure or self-loosening occurs for each grip length. Fig. 5 shows a finite element model of a bolted joint.

FE analysis was conducted using Marc-Mentat 21.1. The external thread of the bolt and the internal thread of the lower clamped plate were modelled with spiral screw threads. In the previous study, fatigue failure occurred in all bolted joints. Therefore FE analyses were conducted for the grip lengths $l_g=6 \text{ mm}$, 9 mm and 12 mm in order to investigate the phenomenon at shorter grip lengths and to reveal the thresholds for fatigue failure and self-loosening. The nominal lengths l of the bolts were $l=21 \text{ mm}$, 24 mm and 27 mm and the thickness of the upper clamped plate was the same as the grip length l_g as shown in Fig. 5. The material properties used in the FE models are shown in Table 2. Young's modulus E of all parts was set to 206 GPa, and Poisson's ratio was set to 0.3. The frictional coefficients between bearing surfaces were set to $\mu=0.1$, and the friction coefficients between the clamped plates were set to $\mu=0$.

TABLE 2 Mechanical properties of test bolt (property class: 8.8)

Young's modulus E	Poisson's ratio ν	Friction coefficient between bearing surfaces μ
206 GPa	0.3	0.1

In the FE analysis model, the upper surface of the lower clamped plate was constrained in the y direction, the left side surface of the lower clamped plate was constrained in the x direction, and the

back surface of the lower clamped plate was constrained in the z direction. In the FE analysis, the initial clamping force F_i was generated by applying a fixed displacement to produce $F_i=15$ kN on the lower surface of the upper clamped part in the $-y$ direction. After the clamp force F_i was applied to the bolted joint, we applied a transverse force P_t to the upper clamped part in the x direction, as shown in Fig. 5. FE analyses were conducted for values of P_t from 1.3 kN to 1.55 kN for each grip length. In this FE analysis, self-loosening was identified by measuring the bolt rotation when applying a cyclic transverse load.

The occurrence of fatigue failure was judged using the following procedures. First, we calculated the bending moment M_B at the root of the first threaded portion from the normal stress in the y direction at each node at the root of the incomplete thread. Specifically, after we calculated the mean stress σ_x of the normal stress in the y direction at Node x_i, x_{i+1}, x_j and x_{j+1} as shown in Fig. 6, we calculated the minute bending moment dM_B of the element by multiplying the mean stress σ_x by the distance $\bar{x}$. Then, the bending moment M_B was calculated by integrating all the minute bending moments dM_B . After that, we calculated the nominal stress σ_t at the root of the first threaded portion

FIGURE 5 FE model of the bolted joint subjected to transverse force

by substituting the bending moment into Eq.(4). If the nominal stress σ_t exceeded the fatigue strength σ_{fw} , we judged that fatigue failure had occurred.

FIGURE 6 Calculation of the bending moment from the FE analysis results

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conditions Causing Fatigue Failure and Self-loosening

Figure 7 shows the nominal stress σ_t at the root of the first thread and the slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface between the bolt head and clamped part plotted against the transverse force P_t for grip length $l_g=12$ mm. In Fig. 7, the left ordinate is the nominal stress σ_t and the right ordinate is the slippage δ_{w-slip} . The abscissa is the transverse force P_t .

It can be seen in Fig. 7 that the nominal stress σ_t increased consistently with an increase in transverse force P_t . However, the slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface only increased slightly up to

FIGURE 7 Nominal stress at the root of the first thread and slippage between bearing surfaces δ_{w-slip} versus the transverse force P_t (Grip length $l_g=12$ mm)

$P_t=1.40$ kN, and then the slippage δ_{w-slip} increased rapidly at $P_t=1.50$ kN. This indicates that the transverse force P_t had exceeded the friction force generated by the initial clamping force F_i . When the bearing surface slipped, as shown in Fig. 7, it can be considered that self-loosening has started. However, the transverse fatigue strength σ_{tw} was $\sigma_{tw}=59.7$ MPa, as shown by Eq.(7). Since the nominal stress σ_t has already exceeded σ_{tw} when $P_t=1.50$ kN, the point at which self-loosening occurs, fatigue failure of bolt has already occurred before the onset of self-loosening. Next, in cases where the slippage δ_{w-slip} increased substantially, we investigated the bolt behaviour to see whether self-loosening really occurred or not.

Figure 8 shows the bolt rotation angle ϕ due to cyclic self-loosening when the bolted joint received a cyclic transverse force. The grip length of this model was $l_g=12$ mm. In Fig. 8, the ordinate is the position on the bolt axis, and the abscissa is the bolt rotation angle ϕ . Before the bolted joint experienced the transverse force P_t , the relationship is a straight line because the bolt does not deform. After the bolted joint is subjected to the transverse force P_t for one cycle, the line is curved and shifts to the right side, indicating that the bolt as rotated as shown by the first cycle line in Fig. 8. After the bolted joint undergoes two cycles of P_t , the axis curves even more and shifts further to the right, denoting increased rotation as shown by the second cycle line. It can be seen in Fig.8 that self-loosening progresses due to the transverse force P_t if the slippage at the bearing surface has occurred irreversibly. In this study, we considered the occurrence of identifiable slippage at the bearing surface to indicate self-loosening.

Figure 9 shows the nominal stress σ_t at the root of the first thread and slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface plotted against transverse force P_t for grip length $l_g=9$ mm. In Fig. 9, the ordinates and the abscissa are the same as in Fig. 7. A chain line at $\sigma_t=59.7$ MPa shows the transverse fatigue strength σ_{tw} .

FIGURE 8 Bolt rotation angle due to the cyclic transverse force for grip length $l_g=12$ mm

It can be seen in Fig. 9 that the nominal stress σ_t increased with an increase in transverse force P_t . It can also be seen that the slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface increased significantly at $P_t=1.50$ kN. However, since the nominal stress σ_t at $P_t=1.50$ kN has already exceeded the transverse fatigue strength $\sigma_{tw}=59.7$ MPa, it can be considered that fatigue failure of the bolt has already occurred before self-loosening occurred.

Figure 10 shows the nominal stress σ_t and slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface versus transverse force P_t for grip length $l_g=6$ mm. In Fig. 10, the ordinates and the abscissa are the same as in Fig. 7. It can be seen in Fig. 10 that the nominal stress σ_t increased with an increase in the transverse force P_t . It can be also seen that the slippage δ_{w-slip} at the bearing surface increased substantially at $P_t=1.55$ kN; so self-loosening appears to happen around $P_t=1.50$ kN. Since the criterion for fatigue failure is whether σ_t exceeds $\sigma_{tw}=59.7$ MPa or not, fatigue failure has not yet occurred, therefore it appears that self-loosening has preceded failure by fatigue.

From these results, the boundary between self-loosening and fatigue failure exists between the grip lengths $l_g=9$ mm and $l_g=6$ mm. Consequently, if the grip length is less than the bolt size, we should consider self-loosening rather than fatigue failure.

Incidentally, we have not considered the friction between the clamped parts in this study. Since it is often pointed out that friction between the clamped parts is important, we should discuss the usefulness of the results of this study. Fig. 11 shows the displacement δ_h of the bolt head versus the transverse force P_t for the frictional coefficient μ between the clamped parts $\mu=0$ and $\mu=0.1$. The grip length of the results was $l_g=12$ mm. In Fig. 11, the ordinate is the displacement δ_h of the bolt head and the abscissa is the transverse force P_t . It can be seen in Fig. 11 that the transverse force P_t was significantly different for $\mu=0$ and $\mu=0.1$ in order to get the same displacement δ_h of the bolt head. However, the same level of displacement δ_h occurred for both friction conditions even if the transverse force P_t was different. The nominal stress in the bolt due to the bending moment is generated due by the displacement δ_h . The results show that the bolt deforms to the same extent even though the transverse force P_t with friction between the clamped parts was larger than the frictionless

FIGURE 9 Nominal stress at the root of the first thread and slippage between bearing surfaces δ_{w-slip} versus the transverse force P_t (Grip length $l_g=9$ mm)

case. Therefore, even though we do not take the friction between the clamped parts into account, the model can simulate the actual situation and provide useful insight into the conditions for self-loosening and fatigue failure.

CONCLUSIONS

We investigated the influence of bolt grip length on self-loosening as well as fatigue failure by conducting FE analysis and comparing the results with the transverse fatigue tests from our previous study. The conclusions obtained in this study are summarized as follows.

FIGURE 10 Nominal stress at the root of the first thread and slippage between bearing surfaces δ_{w-slip} versus the transverse force P_t (Grip length $l_g=6$ mm)

FIGURE 11 Bolt rotation angle due to the cyclic transverse force for each bolted joint with different grip length l_g (Grip length $l_g=12$ mm)

1. It was found that fatigue failure occurs before self-loosening if significant slippage between bearing surfaces does not occur.
2. It was seen that fatigue failure occurs before self-loosening when the grip length is greater than 9 mm, which is slightly smaller than the M10 bolt size.
3. For M10 bolts, it was observed that the threshold of whether self-loosening or fatigue failure occurs, lies between grip lengths 6 mm and 9 mm. Consequently, if the grip length is less than the bolt size, we should consider self-loosening rather than fatigue failure to be the dominant failure mode of the bolted joint.

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